

LAKBAY-DIWA ✦
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME I ISSUE VIII

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

DECEMBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VIII (December 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

CAROL B. ANGLUBEN, MAENGL

Teacher III

Baguio Central University
Baguio City, CAR, Philippines
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17813305

Pribado: Breaking Cultural Taboos in Child Protection

Tony Fowler released her song “Pribado” featuring Tito Vince and Papi Galang on October 31, 2025. The song serves as a reminder for the parents to teach their children about their body parts and to make it clear that no one should touch them in an unsafe manner. It emphasizes that private parts must be protected and that no one should touch them without permission. Furthermore, it teaches children to say “no” when someone violates their boundaries and encourages them to tell their parents or guardians if anyone attempts to touch them inappropriately.

The chorus of the song reminds children:

“Mali ‘yan, h’wag mo ‘kong hawakan, isusumbong kita kay nanay at kay tatay. Pribadong parte ng katawan, iniingatan.”

Translated, it means: “That’s wrong, don’t touch me; I’ll tell mommy and daddy. Private parts of the body must be protected.”

Instead of avoiding the topic, Tony Fowler takes the courage to address the sensitive and serious issue: child sexual abuse and the importance of open communication. This clear and straightforward message about consent makes “Pribado” not just for entertainment, but also a valuable educational tool for families, teachers, and even child- welfare advocates.

The significance of this song becomes even more relevant when viewed alongside actual data. According to the Baguio City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO), from January to June 2025, there were 83 child abuse cases, 52 were female while 21 were male. Among these were 33 cases of incest rape, 13 cases of act of lasciviousness, and 7 sexual molestation. These statistics reveal an alarming situation that needs everyone’s attention. Therefore, teaching children how to protect themselves and where to seek help become crucial.

In the Cordillera region, discussing private parts is often considered uncomfortable. Parents or guardians commonly use euphemisms such as “bird” referring to male private part and “flower” for the female private part. While these terms are culturally familiar, they may cause confusions to the children and prevent them from fully understanding what is safe and what is not.

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VIII (December 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

This is where “Pribado” becomes especially relevant because it addresses these cultural gaps by using clear and direct language. The song introduces the correct anatomical terms and equip them with knowledge about their own bodies and personal boundaries. By doing so, it empowers children to recognize unsafe behavior and protect themselves when someone violates their boundaries. Parents or guardians can use the song as a simple and powerful tool to help their children understand consent, safety and how to respond in potentially risky situations.